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DEVELOPMENT OF «GREEN» AGRICULTURAL SERVICES IN THE CONTEXT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN580

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DEVELOPMENT OF «GREEN» AGRICULTURAL SERVICES IN THE CONTEXT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The development of environmentally friendly agricultural services, considered an important type of service, in the republic was studied based on the available economic opportunities. This article also discusses the features of the development of green agroforestry, organizational and economic mechanisms, ways of modernization and diversification, and directions of development.

Keywords: Agrotourism, green agrotourism, agricultural production, organizational and economic mechanisms of green agrotourism, modernization of green agrotourism, diversification of green agrotourism, digital technologies developing green agrotourism, financial advantages of green agrotourism.

Annotatsiya. Xizmat ko'rsatishning muhim turi hisoblangan yashil agroxizmatlarni respublikada rivojlantirish mavjud iqtisodiy imkoniyatlardan kelib chiqqan holda o'rganilgan. Shuningdek, mazkur maqolada yashil agroxizmatlarni rivojlantirishda o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari, modernizatsiyalash va diversifikatsiyalash yullari, taraqqiyot yo'nalishlari asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Agroxizmat, yashil agroxizmat, agrar sohada ishlab chiqarish, yashil agroxizmatning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari, yashil agroxizmatni modernizatsiyalash, yashil agroxizmatni diversifikatsiyalash, yashil agroxizmatni rivojlantiruvchi raqamli texnologiyalar, yashil agroxizmatning moliyaviy richaglari.

Аннотация. Развитие экологически чистых агросервисов, считающихся важным видом услуг, в республике изучалось исходя из имеющихся экономических возможностей. Также в данной статье рассматриваются особенности развития зеленого агролесомелиорации, организационные и экономические механизмы, пути модернизации и диверсификации, направления развития.

Ключевые слова: Агротуризм, зеленый агротуризм, производство в аграрной сфере, организационные и экономические механизмы зеленого агротуризма, модернизация зеленого агротуризма, диверсификация зеленого агротуризма, цифровые технологии, развивающие зеленый агротуризм, финансовые преимущества зеленого агротуризма.

INTRODUCTION

One of the important foundations of the rapid development of the economy of our republic is the formation of a "green economy". The establishment of systemic activities of the "green economy" in Uzbekistan is directly related to the development of the agricultural network, especially with the development of agrotourism.

In the formation of a "green economy" in the agricultural sector of the Republic, green agro-services are purposeful activities that comprehensively meet the needs for agro-services, which is formed on the basis of consumer demand and supply in a market economy and is based on modern methods and technologies that create the possibility of "environmentally friendly" production.

In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.As Mirziyoyev noted in his address to the Supreme Assembly: "Centers of knowledge and innovation in agriculture will be created in all regions,

where more than 100 agro-services will be created on the principle of a single window. These centers provide important services related to improving land quality, disease control, and seed selection.”

Also in our republic, “as noted in the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026,” the system of agro-services based on science and innovation is being improved. Providing agro-industrial enterprises with raw materials and increasing production volumes to 1.5 barrels” is defined as an important strategic task.

Agricultural service enterprises, providing most of their services, are involved in the process of producing agricultural products from sohada and directly affect the level of production. This is especially important in the formation of a “green economy” in our Republic.

Green agro-services are a set of targeted measures aimed at meeting the needs for the production of environmentally friendly products and the introduction of “green services” into the agricultural sector in a digital economy, and aimed at generating income during its implementation, using modern technologies and digital management technologies. technologies for this purpose.

In the system of forming a “green economy” in the Republic, agricultural services consist of a complex of services that, in addition to growing agricultural products, are carried out during the preparation, drying, storage and placement of grown products, transportation and delivery of seedlings of various crops and trees to create istemolders and other similar processes. Also, “ensuring the implementation of tasks such as “planting 200 million seedlings per year and expanding green areas in cities by more than 1 billion by increasing the total number of seedlings by more than 30 percent,”¹ as indicated separately in Resolution PQ-436 of December 12, 2022 “on measures to improve the effectiveness of reforms, aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

In the context of the digital economy, the concepts of “green economy” and “green agrotourism” as an economic category have a number of characteristics that make it necessary to conduct in-depth research. In this regard, scientists and specialists in this field have outlined a number of approaches and scientific views.

In this regard, American scientist Juan Garcia expressed the idea that “our planet is in a state of ecological crisis today, and the best chance to save it is a green economy”². Lorenzo Martinez, who has also conducted other scientific research in the same field, argues that “the green economy is not only an environmental technology, but also an important new business model that changes the world for the better.”³ According to another foreign economist, Markus Schmidt, “economic growth and concern for the environment are closely linked. The green economy is an opportunity to solve this problem at the same time.”⁴

Another expert in the field, Leonardo Fernandez, insisted that “the green economy requires an innovative approach to new thinking. It’s not just our economy, it’s a call for us to change our way of life.”⁵

According to Russian scientist Yulia Ivanova, “the decision to introduce green technologies is important not only from the point of view of high economic interest, but also, most importantly, from the point of view of its environmental priority.”⁶

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In conducting this study, scientific conclusions were drawn using the methods of analysis and synthesis, comparison, economic statistical analysis, and expert evaluation of scientific research.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Research on the rational organization of green agricultural services in the system of formation of a “green economy” in our republic, assessment and improvement of their effectiveness have significant scientific and practical significance.

Today, the need to develop environmentally friendly agroorganisms, which are considered an important basis for the formation of a “green economy”, is reflected in the following:

v The introduction of a “green service” and the availability of farms and farmsteads and land plots attached to them that meet the requirement of a “green economy” for the cultivation of “environmentally friendly” agricultural products;

1 PQ-436-coh 02.12.2022. 2030-yilgacha O‘zbekiston Respublikasining “yashil” iqtisodiyotga o‘tishiga qaratilgan islohotlar samaradorligini oshirish bo‘yicha chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida (lex.uz)

2 <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Juan-Garcia-41>

3 <https://ideas.repec.org/f/pse263.html>

4 https://translated.turbopages.org/proxy_u/en-ru.ru.df310a55-6649dcf8-ae77f5d0-74722d776562/https/particracy.fandom.com/wiki/Markus_Schmidt

5 <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Leonardo-Fernandes-26>

6 <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Yulia-Ivanova-3>

- ❖ The extent to which the introduction of “green service” and the development of “environmentally friendly” products are provided with sufficient financial resources in farms and farmers;
- ❖ The degree of modernization and diversification of agricultural sectors and enterprises in accordance with the requirements of “green agrotourism” ;
- ❖ The introduction of “Green service” through the provision of high-quality and timely green agricultural services and the availability of opportunities for growing “environmentally friendly” agricultural products and achieving high efficiency;
- ❖ Based on Jaxon’s experience, this moment is characterized by an approved development strategy aimed at creating high-quality and low-quality environmentally friendly agro-services that form a “green economy”.

One of the main conditions for the organization of green agrotourism in the conditions of the modern digital economy is the expedient use of types and technologies of “green” agrotourism for the objects of this system, based on modern global “green” technological achievements. Indeed, based on favorable conditions for the systematic development of the industry, it is advisable to take into account important aspects, features that distinguish it from other industries and industries.

As mentioned above, «green» agroorganisms also cover all other economic and social processes related to agricultural Soha. In this regard, it is especially necessary to increase the number of modern types of green agroforestry, organize high-quality process maintenance, modernize the industry and diversify it in accordance with the needs of consumers(Figure 1).

Figure 1. THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE MECHANISMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF «GREEN AGROFORESTRY»

Modernizing the sphere is considered important in the development of green agro-tourism in Uzbekistan, which is expressed in the following characteristic aspects:

- Increase the intensity of today's and future Green agro-tourism on the basis of the requirements of the «green economy» of the agrarian sector;
- The widespread use of digital technologies, especially artificial intelligence, in the organization and development of green agroforestry;
- Formation of the national system of «green economic space» on the basis of the formation of the green agri-tourism market in the Republic and increasing the competitiveness of the participants in the activities;
- It consists in active participation in the implementation of the Republican «green economy» system, which provides innovation management processes and financial and economic relations, ensuring the qualitative implementation of green agro-tourism.

Also, the main motives for diversifying green agro-tourism in the formation of «green economy» in the Republic are characterized by:

- To increase and increase the volume of new types of green agroforestry display, which allows the production of «environmentally friendly» products based on the implementation of the «Green service».
- Moving interaction and integration in the performance of green agro-services in the process of production of «environmentally friendly» products through the implementation of the «Green service».
- Implementation of the «green Service» and the production of «environmentally friendly» products to reduce the costs of green agro-tourism and achieve high efficiency.
- Effective use of resurtejamkor technologies and intensive factors in the development of green agro-service enterprises and in improving the efficiency of green services.

In fact, in the modernization of green agro-tourism, all directions of the agrarian sphere (economic, organizational, financial, social, management, personnel supply, etc.) it creates opportunities for intensive development of green agroforestry on the basis of modern innovation (digital) technologies, with targeted and targeted involvement of all investment resources and resources in the activities of its constituent entities. It also consists of a system of measures to increase the range of new green services in diversification of green agro-tourism, increase the amount and amount of environmentally friendly products in the field, increase new types of green services and form segments of the green agro-tourism market.

The development of green agro-tourism in our republic, on the one hand, creates opportunities for the effective use of green services by producing environmentally friendly products for the population, on the other hand, increases the efficiency of the industry, leads to an increase in the value of gross product in agriculture. During the research work, the dependence of the increase in the value of gross product in agriculture on green agro-organisms came to economic conclusions using the methods of econometric analysis. Correlation-regression methods of econometric analysis were used to carry out this research process. According to the results of the study, the indicators of the volume of production of agricultural gross product in the Samarkand region were evaluated, and the necessary information was taken from the official site of the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.⁷ According to the results of the analysis, the following were selected as the main factors affecting the volume of production (volume of agricultural gross output) in the conditions of the region:

$Y - Y$ — gross agricultural product, billion soums;

$X_1 - X_1$ — the volume of environmentally friendly products (services) produced by their subjects in agriculture, billion soums;

$X_2 - X_2$ — «green» arable land in agriculture, thousand hectares;

$X_3 - X_3$ — the volume of products (waste) issued by the industrial enterprise for agriculture, billion soums;

$X_4 - X_4$ — revenues from the provision of green agro-services, million soums;

Analysis showed that these factors had the strongest impact on the volume of agricultural output in the province. As a result, the following conclusions were drawn that the income from Green agro-services in the Samarkand region

1 mln. the increase in the amount brought the agricultural gross product to 34 million. 1 billion of the products grown by the entities operating in the sum and in the network (farm and peasant farms). the increase in the amount will increase the amount of gross product to 108 million rubles. provides an increase in the amount.

⁷ <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Leonardo-Fernandes-26>

This trend can be explained in the following years by the introduction of innovative green technologies in the system of rendering green agro-services in the Samarkand region, the effective implementation of measures to diversify and modernize the activities of economic entities, the increase in the number of subjects based on private ownership, the creation of wide opportunities for the effective use of their resources in agriculture

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the main directions for the development of green agro-tourism, calculated from the driving forces of the agrarian economy of Uzbekistan, are as follows. Including:

1. Formation of a system for the development of green agro-tourism according to the principle of “waste-free technology” based on the modernization, diversification, use of modern technologies in accordance with the requirements of the digital economy;

2. The focus of green agro-tourism on increasing the size of the growing Republic in accordance with the requirements of the agrarian sector, strengthening mutual integration ties, reducing its costs and achieving high income with the effective use of intensive factors;

3. Improvement of organizational and economic mechanisms in accordance with the requirements of the digital economy, formation of the organizational structure of the optimal sphere, establishment of integrated activities on the basis of a cluster system as an important direction for the development of green agro-tourism.

4. The formation of norms, norms and standards on the basis of international demand in the field on the basis of new requirements for the organization of effective activities of green agro-tourism.

5. Effective use of incentive mechanisms that prioritize the effective use of bank-credit, financial assets and tax benefits that ensure the development of green agro-services.

In general, Green Agro-Services, which are considered an important regulator of the development of the Republican “green” economy, on the one hand, provide the growing population of the Republic with “environmentally friendly” food products, and industry with “environmentally friendly” food, on the other hand, create new jobs in our country with excess labor, serve as an important source of poverty reduction.

Based on the above, the main recommendations for the development of green agro-tourism in the formation of a “green economy” in Uzbekistan consist of the following:

First of all, the widespread use of the “green agro-security” system in the Republic, corresponding to the demand for the “green economy” and ensuring its progress;

Secondly, as an economic result of the development of the “green economy”, the implementation of the “green Service” and the achievement of the cultivation of “environmentally friendly” agricultural products;

Thirdly, the main basis of the formation of the “green economy” is the modernization and diversification of green agro-organisms into the wool;

Fourth, the development of the “green economy” in our Republic on the basis of the “green agro-security” system using digital technologies;

Fifth, it consists in the effective use of all financial, economic, technological resources in the implementation of the development strategy for 2030 for the development of green agro-tourism in Uzbekistan, corresponding to the “green economy”.

REFERENCES:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisi Qonunchilik palatasi Kengashining 07.01.2021 yildagi “O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti SH.M.Mirziyoyevning 2020-yil 29-dekabrda Oliy Majlis va O'zbekiston xalqiga murojaatnomasida bayon etilgan takliflar va xulosalardan kelib chiqadigan vazifalar to'g'risida” qarori, 681-IV-son
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 28.01.2022 yildagi “2022 — 2026-yillarga mo'ljallangan Yangi O'zbekistonning Taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risida” Farmoni, PF-60-son
3. Қ.Ж Мирзаев, Э.Ш. Шавқиев, Б.К. Жанзаков. Инновацион иқтисодиёт. (Уқув кулланма - Т.: «Инновацион ривожланиш нашриёт-матбаа уйи»,2020. - 298 бет.
4. Мирзаев Қ.Ж. Агросервис иқтисодиёти. Монография.-Т.:“ИQTISOD-MOLIYA” нашриёти, 2013. - 212 Б. - 13,25 б.т.
5. Mirzaev K. The market livestock service of the Republic Uzbekistan // Spanish journal of rural development University of Santiago de Compostela. Volume II, - No2. Spain. 2011. - P. 97-106.
6. Mirzaev K. Approaches and issues for developing livestock services in Uzbekistan // International Cross-Industry Research Journal Perspectives of Innovations, Economics and Business. Volume 8, Issue 2, Praga. 2011.- P. 23-25.
7. “Agro-services in Uzbekistan: Status, Problems and Prospects” - Наида Исмаилова, “Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development”, Volume 6, Issue 2, 2015.
8. “Agro-Service Markets in Central Asia: The Role of Contract Farming” - Интизор Назарова, “Eurasian Journal of Business and Economics”, Volume 10, Issue 20, 2017.
9. PQ-436-сон 02.12.2022. 2030-yilgacha O'zbekiston Respublikasining “yashil” iqtisodiyotga o'tishiga qaratilgan islohotlar samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida (lex.uz)
10. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Juan-Garcia-41>

11. <https://ideas.repec.org/f/pse263.html>
12. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Leonardo-Fernandes-26>
13. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Yulia-Ivanova-3>
14. www.stat.uz

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